

Modernise log collection of OKD deployments

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AUTHOR(S):

Christian Klempau
CERN IT Platforms & Infrastructure

SUPERVISOR(S):

Alberto Pimpo
Chrysoula Dikonimaki

PROJECT SPECIFICATION

This project aims at providing an improved log collection, processing, and storage pipeline for the internal logging events occurring inside all of the OKD clusters, such as PaaS, WebEOS, Drupal and App-Catalogue, where scientists, researchers, and employees can request access to the internal cluster and get resources provisioned to them. Specifically, the project will be divided into three stages:

- **Research and evaluation**

Investigate and document existing solutions and technologies for logging pipelines. Research how other CERN projects approached the problem. Document in detail each one of the shortcomings, advantages and use cases from the previous findings for each of the technologies. Investigate the feasibility of having a solution working for both for OKD and Kubernetes Magnum.

- **Small scale implementation**

Deploy a complete pipeline in a simple but real project, in order to gain knowledge about the potential implementation obstacles, considerations or limitations and getting to know the technologies. Since the deployment will occur in a production environment, it will already be a benefit to the organization.

- **Proof of concept**

Configure a proof of concept logging pipeline solution for OKD deployments in our clusters in addition to Kubernetes Magnum, in case of technical feasibility.

ABSTRACT

To address future processing demands, it's essential to enhance logging capabilities by implementing a more robust, efficient, and maintainable system, in replacement of our current Fluentd system. In addition, OKD maintainer RedHat already deprecated Fluentd log collector Operator and plans to phase out and remove it in a future release, providing only bug fixes and support in the meantime. Their official alternative is Vector for the internal log collector Operator, which is our chosen option for researching and proof of concept.

Fluentd is an open source data collector and processor used as a general purpose logging tool written in Ruby, under the CNCF. Fluentbit serves the same purpose, also under the CNCF, but is written in C, which makes it faster and more memory efficient. Vector is also a logging collector and processor that serves the same purpose, but is written in Rust and is developed by DataDog.

This report details the research and modifications to the internal OKD logging pipeline out of Fluentd towards FluentBit and Vector in order to match the current system requirements, make it more robust and efficient, and also be compatible with future releases of OKD. Also, we will explore ways to simplify the logging pipeline itself, merging different components into one aggregator.

Our OKD telemetry pipeline collects logs from containers and Kubernetes itself, parses them, and sends them to OpenSearch, through the Central Monitoring system. Our Kubernetes Magnum clusters implement almost the same pipeline, in addition to enriching the data with metrics about the logs themselves, in order to send them to Prometheus. Therefore, we will try to make our solution cross-compatible for OKD and Kubernetes Magnum.

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1. Introduction and context

a. Telemetry

To understand logging, we need to first understand telemetry: it refers to the automated collection, transmission and storage of data from various systems and applications to monitor and analyze their performance, behavior, and health. It is used to gain insights, for compliance, traceability, and system status monitoring for correct IT administration.

Over the big umbrella of telemetry, we classify three components: logs, metrics and traces. Firstly, metrics are a measurement of a service captured at runtime. Each metric consists of not only the measurement itself, but also the time at which it was captured. They act as important indicators of availability and performance. Then, traces are a collection of structured logs with context, correlation, and hierarchy. They are useful to give us the big picture of what happens and its path when a request is made to an application. Finally, logs are a time stamped text record, usually structured, from information, debug information, warning and errors.

b. Logging

In this project, we will specifically focus on logging, given the shorter project timespan limitations, although most of the technologies we analyzed also support traces and / or metrics. Logs often contain detailed debugging or diagnostic info, such as inputs to an operation, the result of the operation, and any support metadata to the operation. The act of logging consists in emitting a log record to any source, being over network, through a file, stdout or any other mechanism.

c. How logging tools work

All common logging technologies work with the **sources** → **transformers** → **sinks** pattern. It is also called **input** → **filter** → **output**, depending on the logging processor.

Figure 1: logging tools generic workflow

In Figure 1, we can see the general pattern of many sources, to one processor to many sinks. The first step is data collection: it can come in different forms and depends on each processor which it supports. In general, they all strongly support logging in different ways such as file tailing, stdout, HTTP, Kubernetes and others. In general, the log aggregators have first-party or plugin support for different types of inputs, in order to connect to the source and parse the logs seamlessly in a standardized output.

The second step is first processing the logs. The system can filter logs and discard them based on specific rules. It can also tag the logs in order to redirect them to a specific processing pipeline, while also modifying the fields, transforming the data or even enriching it with further data. It can also aggregate multiple sources into one log pipeline, while also buffering the output in time, size or quantity to sinks.

The last step of the logging pipeline is the output or sinking process. Its point is to send the already filtered and processed logs to another service, or to save them. It is up to the output process to decide what to do with the received logs. Some output services include Elasticsearch, Prometheus, message queues, topics, to a compressed file, or even any network exposed service.

In general, logging is the most supported element of telemetry inside the aggregators. Some of them support metrics in different stages of development, such as first party support, through plugins, or manually. Traces are in general not supported except if you configure them manually.

d. The golden standard

The historical golden standard of logging pipeline is known as the ELK stack. Elasticsearch, LogStash and Kibana. LogStash is one of the first tools to collect, process and save logs in a unified way. LogStash generally collects and processes the logs, and then sends them to Elasticsearch. The latter acts as a database and search engine, where Kibana acts as a user-friendly way of analyzing, observing and filtering them.

We at CERN already use Kibana and OpenSearch (ElasticSearch alternative), provided as a service by the OpenSearch team.

Despite this, we do not use LogStash, since the Kubernetes space started using new tools such as Fluentd instead, because of its modular design and it being community driven through the CNCF.

e. How we currently use Fluentd

Figure 2: architecture with Fluentd aggregator

We currently use a Kubernetes Operator called [OpenShift Logging Operator](#). It is designed to deploy a full-stack configuration using Fluentd, OpenSearch and Grafana together. Since we at CERN already have a central service both for OpenSearch and Grafana, we only end up using the operator to deploy Fluentd.

What the Logging Operator deploys using Fluentd is not enough for our requirements. It is capable of getting system logs from both nodes and container logs from the pods, but we also need some processing on top of this gathered data, in addition to data enrichment with events and proxy accesses. Given this consideration, we deployed another Fluentd system, in this case a StatefulSet to collect the logs from the various sources. Another problem faced in the past is that Fluentd is not able to collect Kubernetes events, therefore we were forced to deploy FluentBit too, which supports said collection.

In Figure 2, you can observe the current architecture for the Fluentd collector. It gets logs both from the Fluentd daemonset forwarder and from HAProxy, transforms them and outputs them to the central monitoring system that uses OpenSearch.

f. Why do we need an upgrade?

Log collection, processing, storage and retrieval is becoming an important issue to address in large organizations with enormous web traffic, data processing and cloud computing requirements like CERN. It enables real-time monitoring and alerting, which are crucial for maintaining the health and correct operation of IT infrastructure. For organizations with complex architectures such as CERN, it also provides visibility into the operations, helping to identify and troubleshoot any occurring issues. Secondly, logs are essential for security and compliance purposes, since they record access to our systems, assisting in threat detection and usage analysis.

Given the previous points, a fully working logging pipeline is vital to CERN. Therefore, we need to ensure the correct operation of it in our internal systems.

Fluentd is a community driven open source project created by the company Treasure Data. The company does not actively contribute nor support the tool anymore, and is pushing users towards FluentBit. While the community still contributes, there is no active development anymore. Given that, the OpenShift Logging Operator that we use inside OKD will discontinue its support for Fluentd in favor of Vector.

While our current implementation of Fluentd is working as expected and no logs are lost, it can still happen that it crashes due to its memory inefficiency. Thanks to the nature of Kubernetes and its self-healing mechanism, in contrast to VMs, even if containers crash they will still recover automatically. Therefore, it would be beneficial to migrate away from Fluentd to more modern, scalable, efficient and supported solutions.

Finally, we will also explore further ways of improving the logging pipeline, specifically through intelligent anomaly detection. We will dive into the “Anomaly Detection” OpenSearch feature. It promises to generate alerts on unusual behavior changes in our logging data, providing insights into our data. It uses Random Cut Forests (RCF), an unsupervised machine learning algorithm that models the incoming data and assigns an anomaly grade and confidence score for each incoming input data point.

2. Research and evaluation of Vector

a. Decision: rework the logging system

We decided to rebuild the logging system into a unified one, with a new tool. We will consider Vector and FluentBit as alternatives. The goal is to achieve a daemonset collector, and only one central aggregator and processor.

As requirements, we need the new system to be functionally identical to the previous system. Also, if technically possible, it would be ideal to have compatibility not only with OKD, but also with Kubernetes Magnum.

b. Starting point

In order to act on our choice and make a more informed decision, we need to gain more experience and knowledge on these two new tools being Vector and FluentBit. We wanted to obtain real world experience with these tools before using them in a big project. Therefore, I contributed to the legacy-web-redirector project, implementing logging capabilities for it. Given that Vector is the new choice for the upstream OKD operator, we chose Vector as a starting point.

c. Available benchmarks

We analyzed the performance benchmarks published by Vector and realized that they were irregular, unkempt, deprecated and biased. In general, the benchmarking project is not maintained anymore, and was developed between 2019 and 2021. Also, the test suite uses old versions of both Vector and FluentBit, with a negative bias towards FluentBit by using an older version at the time period by almost 3 years. Further research and benchmarks need to be done with versions of FluentBit > 3.0 and Vector > 0.3. Therefore, the presented official benchmarks are not to be trusted. Here are the versions and dates used for the benchmarks:

Fluentbit = 1.1.0 May 20, 2019, <https://fluentbit.io/announcements/v1.1.0/>

Vector = 0.20.0 February 8, 2022, <https://vector.dev/releases/0.20.0/>

Vector test harness, 2019 - 2021 <https://github.com/vectordev/vector-test-harness/>

d. Inner workings

The first step of the project consisted of the research phase of current technologies that solve the organization problems and adjust to their needs. We first came into contact with [Vector](#), from DataDog. It is described as a high-performance observability data pipeline, capable of collecting, transforming, and routing logs, metrics, and traces to any supported vendors. It works in a **sources** → **transformers** → **sinks** architecture, as all common logging technologies explained before.

i. Sources

Sources are defined as inputs to the pipeline. Vector supports all kinds of sinks, from simple ones such as standard output and files to more complex ones such as Docker / Kubernetes logs, AWS S3, Prometheus, Kafka topics and RabbitMQ. <https://vector.dev/docs/reference/configuration/sources/>

A simple input sink can be defined as this in a TOML format:

```
[sources.file_logs]
type = "file"
include = [ "/logs/*.log" ]
read_from = "end" # avoids duplicate entries when the vector container restarts
```

ii. Transformers

On the other side, transformers are defined as ways to shape the data as it moves through the configured Vector topology. First, we will discuss the filters of type [VRL or Remap](#). This kind of transformer is meant to shape the incoming data or preprocess it to specific project or organization requirements. VRL is an expression-oriented language designed for transforming logs and metrics, also created and maintained by DataDog.

The main reason why you would want to use VRL is to parse expressions with Regex, add fields, add defaults, and delete fields. In the following example, we show off the main VRL utilities in a transformer:

```
source = '''
  structured =
    parse_regex!(.message, r'^(?P<host>\S*) - (?P<remote_addr>\S*) -
  \[(?P<timestamp>\S* \S*)\] \U{22}(?P<verb>\S*) \U{2F} (?P<protocol>\S*)\U{22}
  (?P<status_code>\d*) (?P<body_bytes_sent>\d*) \U{22}(?P<http_referer>\S*)\U{22}
  \U{22}(?P<user_agent>.*)\U{22}.*$')
  . = merge(., structured)
  .timestamp_str = parse_timestamp(.timestamp, "%d/%b/%Y:%H:%M:%S %z") ?? now()
  .timestamp_int = to_int(.timestamp_str)
  .body_bytes_sent = to_int(.body_bytes_sent) ?? 0
  .status_code = to_int(.status_code) ?? 0
  del(.message)
  del(.timestamp)
'''
```

Variables starting with a dot “.” are global, so they are inserted into the current log pipeline context. Variables that do not start with a dot have their lifecycle only during the transformer execution and get deleted if they do not reflect a change into the global state.

In this example, “structured” is a temporary variable that holds the result of a Regex parsing of the “.message” variable that holds the log. The Regex itself tries to parse the log from Nginx format and

split it into groups, denoted by “?<group>”. Then, in the next line the Regex result gets merged into the global context, where each key is the group name and the value is the matched Regex.

With VRL you can also parse timestamps and use a default with the syntactic sugar of the ternary operator “??”. Finally, we delete some unused fields with the “del” keyword.

Here, the “source” field which holds the VRL expression is wrapped around triple single quotes. The reason is in some specific cases the VRL parser refuses to compile your expression. Note that some characters cannot be matched by their literal or their escape sequence, like the double quotes or the backslash.

The workaround is to use their Unicode. You can [look them up here](#). For example if you want to match these characters, here is how you would do it:

```
" : \U{22}
/ : \U{2F}
```

For example, to match the HTTP verb and protocol in different groups:

```
log: '... "GET / HTTP/1.1" ...'
expression: r'^ ... \U{22}(?P<verb>\S*) \U{2F} (?P<protocol>\S*)\U{22} ... $'
```

A transformer can also be of kind [Filter](#), which essentially only filters out incoming logs and does not let them through the continuation of the pipeline except if a specific condition is met. For example a simple boolean condition:

```
# NOTE: For simple logical expressions, note that you need to use single quotes
# to wrap the value of condition.
# NOTE: The events are filtered when the condition is false,
# that means that as long as the condition is truthy, the logging pipeline will
# continue.
[transforms.remove_from_forwarded_for]
type="filter"
inputs= ["anonymize_ips"]
condition = '.host != "non-important-domain.web.cern.ch"'
```

Another example is filtering logs based on a Regex expression, in this case filter out all of the logs that do not have the field “timestamp_int” as a numeric string:

```
[transforms.filter_bad_timestamp]
type = "filter"
inputs = ["anonymize_ips"]
condition = '''match(to_string(.timestamp_int) ?? "", r'^\d+$') == true'''
```

Note that almost all VRL expressions are fallible, that means they can fail. Therefore, you need to handle the edge cases. For example here, the string conversion can fail.

Also note that you have to be explicit about the comparison and use `== true | false`.

Transformers of type [Reduce](#) and [Aggregate](#) are also available, but will not be discussed due to them not being used in the project. More documentation can be found on their respective links.

iii. Sinks

They act as a delivery system from your observability data to a variety of destinations. We will not go into detail, but present the more common use cases of sinks such as RabbitMQ, S3, AWS SNS / SQS, OpenSearch / Elasticsearch, stdout, file (with or without compression), Kafka, Prometheus, or a custom HTTP output. [You can read more about it here.](#)

iv. Related project

Many of the base configurations were inspired by another CERN project called web-redirector-v2 which already uses Vector, but much more work had to be done on top of it, especially regarding log transformation and sinking. The most helpful configuration taken from web-redirector-v2 was how to use OpenSearch as a sink, especially regarding the CERN CA Root certificate for SSL.

a. Small scale implementation

As mentioned in the starting point, we thought that a contribution to a real project such as legacy-web-redirector was a better way of testing the capabilities, strengths and weaknesses of Vector. Therefore, we implemented logging capabilities for it.

i. Architecture

Figure 3: high level web-redirector architecture

Vector was deployed as a new container inside the web-redirector Pod, which itself is a Kubernetes deployment inside the PaaS cluster, as seen in Figure 3.

The logs are stored by Nginx in a file, in order for Vector to read them line by line. Finally, a new index is created inside OpenSearch for each day, following the format `"vector-%Y-%m-%d"`.

ii. Implementation

We successfully deployed changes to [legacy-redirector](#), adding Vector logging mechanisms, while also adding an OpenSearch sink and aggregator.

In this case, the Vector pipeline is linear: first, we collect the logs from the local file, then we use Regexp to parse the Nginx log, transform and remove the necessary fields, anonymize the IP, and finally send the result to the different sinks, depending on configuration values.

Figure 4: internal Vector processing pipeline

The final format of the logs stored in OpenSearch and in file (when decompressed) is the following:

```

{
  "body_bytes_sent": 145,
  "file": "/logs/access.log",
  "host": "<my-host>.web.cern.ch",
  "http_referer": "-",
  "protocol": "HTTP/1.1",
  "remote_addr": "2001:1458:204::",
  "source_type": "file",
  "status_code": 302,
  "timestamp_int": 1721999427,
  "timestamp_str": "2024-07-26T13:10:27Z",
  "user_agent": "Mozilla/5.0 (X11; Linux x86_64; rv:128.0) Gecko/20100101
Firefox/128.0",
  "verb": "GET"
}

```

The logs saved to a file are Log files are compressed using `zst` and then persisted on a volume. There is a log file for each day, using this format: `vector-%Y-%m-%d`. You cannot `cat` the file to see

the contents. So the best way is to use base64 encoding and transfer them copy and pasting from the integrated terminal.

```
$ base64 log.json.zst
```

You can then copy the output and paste it in another machine to a log.json.zst.b64 file. Then, decode the file and decompress:

```
$ base64 -d log.json.zst.b64 > log.json.zst
```

```
$ zstd -d log.json.zst
```

b. Results

We decided Vector was only suitable for simple projects, but not a suitable option for more complex projects. For bigger projects, FluentBit is a more suitable choice. The main reasons are:

i. Lack of support for VRL

Alternatives like FluentBit have better support through CNCF, while VRL depends on a single maintainer from DataDog.

ii. Low extensibility for VRL syntax

The VRL syntax is restrictive for one-liners, which are sometimes needed such as in filters.

Lua language is also presented as an option to use inside Vector, but [official reports](#) mention a ~60% performance drop. Also, in order to use Lua it was necessary to program complete functions with input and output, adding even more complexity and decreasing readability when alternatives such as VRL or FluentBit can do it in a couple of lines.

iii. Caveats

Regex syntax is convoluted, and lacking documentation, compile and syntax errors are not expressive, and having to learn a new language are considerable caveats for using Vector. Also, edge case handling has to be explicit, while FluentBit and Fluentd can do it automatically.

We conclude that Vector is not a suitable option for larger projects such as the logging collector inside of our OKD clusters, considering all of the previous results that make it unusable for a scalable, maintainable and easy to understand project.

The syntax is not suitable for our needs, making the migration from Fluentd to FluentBit more straightforward since they are more similar. Therefore, we decided to explore FluentBit further.

3. Research and evaluations - OpenSearch feature

a. Research

We decided to research an OpenSearch feature, specifically the “Anomaly Detection” for logs. In order to use anomaly detection, you need to ensure your analyzed data is in a numerical integer format, since it is a requirement for the internal detection algorithm. Also, each feature to analyze has a maximum of 5 inputs. Therefore, you are forced to do either:

- One hot encoding:
 - For example, for HTTP verbs, we can easily encode them in 5 categories. GET, DEL, POST, PATCH / PUT, OTHERS
 - For HTTP return codes, since we have around 10 for each starting with 2, 4 and 5, we need to bin them. Therefore, aggregate all return codes starting with 2 in a 2xx field, and the same for 4xx and 5xx, in order to not go over the 5 input maximum.
- Raw numerical data:
 - For data such as response time or frequencies you can use the numerical value directly.

Also, we explain which aggregation techniques should be used for each use-case:

- **average():** For detecting anomalies in the central tendency of your data. Website or Service response time in ms. Low response time could mean network error, and high response time could mean performance degradation or service saturation.
- **count():** For detecting anomalies in the frequency of events. Tracking 2xx, 4xx, 5xx HTTP response codes. Sudden spike in 4xx and 5xx in addition to drop in 2xx could relate to a service problem.
- **sum(), min(), max():** self explanatory

Figure 5: Example anomaly detection for status codes

In Figure 5, you can observe an anomaly detection inside the OpenSearch dashboard. It works based on probabilistic models, where if in the specified time window the probability distribution changes dramatically, an anomaly occurrence is cataloged. These anomalies can be connected to messaging systems such as Email and Slack as an alert.

c. Results

We also decided to not do further experiments with OpenSearch Anomaly Detection for the following reasons:

i. Manual categorization

Ideally, we would want to input the entire log string and have a ML algorithm analyze it and detect anomalies using a language model, instead of parsing the observable features by hand. Also, this gives low flexibility for different kinds of logs, and forces you to manually create a new pipeline for each traceback, such as Python, Java, Nginx, etc.

ii. Numeric dependency

As said before, the probabilistic features need to be in a numerical format, one-hot encoded which scales in size exponentially or binned which gives poor traceability.

iii. Conclusion

We conclude that OpenSearch anomaly detection current state is not where we need it to be. Data has to manually be encoded and binned for it to be useful, which adds unnecessary complexity to the architecture. Also, features and anomaly detection has to be manually set up, which makes it unmaintainable for the future. We decided that everything metrics related is best done by Prometheus, while keeping OpenSearch only as a log aggregator, short term storage and search engine for users.

4. Proof of concept

Overview

The provided FluentBit configuration implements a comprehensive logging solution for OKD clusters. It's deployed as a DaemonSet, ensuring that a FluentBit instance runs on each node in the cluster. The configuration covers various aspects of log collection, processing, and forwarding, tailored specifically for OKD environments.

Log Sources

The configuration collects logs from multiple sources:

1. Container logs (`/var/log/pods/*/*/*log`)
2. Linux system journal (`/var/log/journal`)
3. Audit logs
 - a. Linux:
 - i. `/var/log/audit/audit.log`
 - b. Kubernetes:
 - i. `/var/log/kube-apiserver/audit.log`
 - c. OpenShift audit logs:
 - i. `/var/log/oauth-apiserver/audit.log`
 - ii. `/var/log/openshift-apiserver/audit.log`
 - iii. `/var/log/oauth-server/audit.log`
 - d. Open Virtual Network (OVN) audit logs:
 - i. `/var/log/ovn/acl-audit-log.log`

Processing and Filtering

The configuration applies several filters and modifications to the collected logs:

1. **Record Modification:**
 - Adds a UUID to each log entry
 - Renames fields for consistency (e.g., `log` to `message`)
2. **Kubernetes Metadata:**
 - Enriches container logs with Kubernetes metadata
3. **Parsing:**
 - Parses JSON messages from the event router
 - Parses OVN audit logs
 - Handles audit log timestamps
4. **Tagging and Rewriting:**
 - Retags journal logs based on their source (e.g., Kibana, event router, system containers)
5. **Custom Processing:**

- Uses Lua scripts for advanced processing

Output

The configuration sets up two outputs:

1. **Standard Output:** For debugging purposes
2. **Forward:** Sends logs to a Fluentd aggregator service in the `openshift-logging` namespace

Custom Lua processing

- Fixing timestamp formats: needed when the log does not have a correctly set timestamp, which is required in Fluentd in a specific format

```
function fix_timestamp(tag, timestamp, record)
  if record["@timestamp"] and record["@timestamp"] ~= "" then
    return 0, timestamp, record
  end

  -- get the decimal part of the timestamp
  nsec = timestamp % 1
  n_sec_str = tostring(nsec)
  -- get the first 9 digits of the decimal part in a string
  nsec_last_digits = n_sec_str:match("%.(%d+)"):sub(1,9)
  -- in UTC (!), format the main timestamp
  formatted_time = os.date("!%Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%S", timestamp)
  -- add the timezone offset, which is +00:00 for UTC
  tz_offset = "+00:00"
  -- concatenate the main timestamp, the decimal part and the timezone
  offset
  full_timestamp = string.format("%s.%s%s", formatted_time,
    nsec_last_digits, tz_offset)
  record["@timestamp"] = full_timestamp
  return 1, timestamp, record
end
```

- Adjusting systemd fields to fit Fluentd requirements

```
function fix_systemd_fields(tag, timestamp, record)
  record["message"] = record["MESSAGE"]
  record["hostname"] = record["_HOSTNAME"]
  record["systemd"] = {
    ["u"] = {
```

```

        ["SYSLOG_FACILITY"] = record["SYSLOG_FACILITY"],
        ["SYSLOG_IDENTIFIER"] = record["SYSLOG_IDENTIFIER"]
    },
    ["t"] = {
        ["SYSTEMD_UNIT"] = record["_SYSTEMD_UNIT"],
        ["PID"] = record["_PID"]
    }
}
return 1, timestamp, record
end

```

- Modifying Kubernetes fields to fit Fluentd requirements

```

function fix_kubernetes_fields(tag, timestamp, record)
    record["hostname"] = record["kubernetes"]["host"]
    record["host"] = nil

    return 1, timestamp, record
end

```

Custom Parsers

Several custom parsers are defined to handle specific log formats:

- **OVN log parser:** specifically used for OVN logs, where the log format is different and we need to extract the first part of it as the log timestamp:

```

[PARSER]
  Name ovn_parser
  Format regex
  Regex ^(?<log_timestamp>[^\|]+).*
  Time_Key log_timestamp
  Time_Format %Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%S.%Lz

```

- **JSON message parser:** needed to parse only a specific key of the log as a JSON:

```

[FILTER]
  Name parser
  Match kubernetes.var.log.pods.*eventrouter*
  Key_Name message
  Parser json_message_parser
  Preserve_Key true
  Reserve_Data true

```

```
...

[PARSER]
  Name json_message_parser
  Format json
```

- **Custom “receivedTimestamp” parser**, needed to parse the data in JSON but also parsing a specific key with a specific time format as the log time:

```
[PARSER]
  Name requestReceivedTimestamp
  Format json
  Time_Key requestReceivedTimestamp
  Time_Keep On
  Time_Format %Y-%m-%dT%H:%M:%S.%N%z
```

- **Kubernetes pod log parser**: extract from the currently parsed log file name part of the necessary Kubernetes metadata, such as namespace name, pod name, docker id and container name:

```
[PARSER]
  Name kube-pod-log
  Format regex
  Reserve_Data true
  Regex
  (?<namespace_name>[a-z0-9](?:[-a-z0-9]*[a-z0-9])?(?:_[a-z0-9]([-a-z0-9]*[a-z0-9])?)?)*_(?<pod_name>[^_+)](?<docker_id>.*)\.(?<container_name>.*)\.log$
```

Key Features

1. **Pods Log Handling**: Supports logs from containers using CRI and Docker parsers
2. **Efficient Log Tailing**: Uses database files to track log file positions
3. **Flexible Filtering**: Implements various filtering mechanisms to process logs based on their source and content
4. **Kubernetes Integration**: Deep integration with Kubernetes, including metadata enrichment and namespace-aware processing
5. **Audit Log Support**: Comprehensive handling of various audit log sources in the OKD environment
6. **Custom Processing**: Uses Lua scripts for advanced log manipulation, allowing for complex transformations

Results

The proof of concept yielded several significant findings:

1. **Pod Log Collection:** functions as expected, but requires custom Regex parsers for accurate collection, in combination with Lua functions for modifications.
2. **Systemd journal Log Collection:** functions as expected, but requires custom Lua functions for collection and modifications.
3. **Lua Functions:** essential for complex parsing tasks, including:
 - Utilizing the internal FluentBit timestamp
 - Accessing or modifying deeply nested structures
 - Performing time parsing in various ways and operating on strings
4. **Container ID Collection:** feasible, but only when collecting pod logs from `/var/log/containers`, a location being deprecated by Kubernetes.
5. **Audit Integration:** does not function correctly due to insufficient plugin support in FluentBit.

Future work

While the proof of concept successfully replaces most of Fluentd's functionality with FluentBit, several areas require further development:

1. **Multiline Log Handling:** Comprehensive testing is needed to ensure proper handling of multiline logs.
2. **Message Tracking:** Implement a hashing mechanism for consistent message tracking, replacing the current UUID system.
3. **Limitations in Metadata Collection:** `container_image_id` and `namespace_id` cannot be collected in FluentBit due to the lack of custom Kubernetes API integration, which is available in Fluentd.
4. **Audit Log Handling:** Migrate this functionality to Fluentd due to lack of Openshift-specific plugins
5. **Custom Plugin Development:** Explore the possibility of developing custom plugins for FluentBit to address specific OKD logging requirements that are currently not met.
6. **Integration Testing:** Perform extensive integration testing with the existing logging ecosystem to ensure seamless compatibility and data consistency.

Conclusion

The FluentBit-based proof of concept demonstrates a viable replacement for the existing Fluentd system in OKD clusters. Key conclusions include:

1. **Viability:** The solution provides a robust and flexible logging framework capable of handling the complexities of OKD environments.
2. **Performance and Maintainability:** FluentBit offers improved performance and maintainability compared to the current Fluentd system.

3. **Functionality Preservation:** Critical logging functionality is maintained, ensuring continuity in log collection and processing.
4. **Adaptability:** The use of Lua scripts showcases the solution's adaptability in addressing OKD-specific requirements and overcoming some of FluentBit's limitations.
5. **Kubernetes Integration:** The proof of concept demonstrates deep integration with Kubernetes, including metadata enrichment and namespace-aware processing.
6. **Challenges:** While largely successful, the implementation revealed some limitations, particularly in audit log handling and certain metadata collection capabilities.
7. **Future-Ready:** The proof of concept lays a strong foundation for future enhancements and optimizations in OKD logging infrastructure.

Having said that, FluentBit configuration provides a robust and flexible logging solution for OKD clusters. It addresses the complexities of collecting logs from various sources in a Kubernetes environment, enriching them with relevant metadata, and preparing them for further processing and analysis. The use of Lua scripts for custom processing demonstrates the adaptability of the solution to specific requirements of the OKD environment.

Therefore, our FluentBit-based proof of concept demonstrates a viable replacement for the existing Fluentd system, offering improved performance and maintainability while preserving critical logging functionality. The use of Lua scripts provided the flexibility needed to overcome FluentBit's limitations and maintain compatibility with our existing logging ecosystem.